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ABSTRACT

Neuromorphic device design demands a clear understanding of the dynamics governing conductance modulation under external stimuli. Many synaptic memristors can be described by a quasi-linear model, where a memory variable relaxes between two limiting states. Here, we derive analytical expressions for the response of such systems to trains of voltage pulses, providing closed formulations for paired-pulse facilitation (PPF), convergent potentiation, and frequency-dependent gain. This approach predicts how the memory variable evolves toward stationary values determined by device and stimulation parameters, offering a compact alternative to numerical simulations. We experimentally validate the model using a nanofluidic memristor based on a nanoporous membrane, showing that the predicted convergence closely matches measured potentiation and that the analytical PPF trends reproduce experimental data. These results establish a unified framework for describing spike-driven plasticity and enable reliable cross-comparison of synaptic behavior across memristive systems, facilitating their integration into neuromorphic circuits.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In biological organisms, the incoming sensory information is transformed into electrical spikes and transmitted in parallel across the extensive network of neuron cells and their synaptic junctions, enabling hearing, vision, taste, emotions, learning, memory, and other perception-related functions. The brain achieves these remarkable cognitive feats while employing a fraction of the power of present-day computers.

Neuromorphic devices aim to exploit the computational architecture of the human brain. Two-terminal memristors with controllable synaptic weights facilitate advanced neural networks^{1,2} with learning and recognition functions.³ Numerous resistive switching systems of this kind have been reported, including semiconductor ion carriers, chalcogenide materials, metal oxides, electrochemical metallization cells, phase change materials, halide perovskites, and fluidic nanochannels.^{4–15} In these systems, a memory variable is related to an ionic redistribution process that reacts to external stimuli, such as filamentary switching in electrochemical metallization cells and interface-type switching by the modification of Schottky barriers.

The neuromorphic computational schemes rely on the ability of gradual switching memristors to emulate key biological functions of synaptic weights.^{1,16} Synaptic plasticity is enabled by intimately coupled signaling pathways and consists of the potentiation/depression by increasing/decreasing the synapse weight under excitatory/inhibitory voltage pulses.¹⁷ The synaptic adaptation, depending on the ordered match of action potentials in pre- and postsynaptic neurons, is described by the paired-pulse facilitation (PPF),^{18–20} spike-rate-dependent plasticity (SRDP), and spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP).^{21,22}

These properties are usually tested experimentally with numerically intensive methods, such as the Poisson–Nernst–Planck (PNP) transport kinetics model.¹⁴ In this paper, we provide analytical insight into these methods. In a pulsed voltage train measurement that emulates a spiking schedule, the memory variable increases during voltage stimulation and decays during the intervals between pulses. As a result, the synaptic state is governed by the dynamic balance between excitation and relaxation phases, ultimately stabilizing at a steady-state value determined by the stimulation parameters and timing of the pulse train. Here, we derive full expressions to describe quantitatively the synapse adaptation based on a

quasi-linear conductance activated memristor (CALM) model that has been recently reviewed.²³ We provide a thorough analysis of PPF, which has been extensively investigated for decades in natural neuromorphic systems^{17,18,24} and, more recently, it has gained strong relevance in artificial synaptic devices.^{25–28} The ability to reproduce this short-term plasticity effect in memristive systems provides not only a benchmark for biomimetic functionality but also a key mechanism for temporal information processing in neuromorphic circuits. These results provide insight into the synapse behavior of more complex memristors, as they show the elementary universal properties of electrical synapses.

II. DYNAMICAL PROPERTIES OF POTENTIATION IN SYNAPTIC MEMRISTORS

Memristors are generally described by the combination of two equations^{29–31}

$$I_{tot} = F(V, x), \tag{1}$$

$$\tau_k(V) \frac{dx}{dt} = g(V, x). \tag{2}$$

Here, I_{tot} is the total current and F is a function that describes the conduction current as a function of the voltage V in the device and a state variable x . The x is a (memory) variable necessary to determine the future behavior of the system when the present state and the inputs are known. The delay effect in the memristor response is expressed in Eq. (2), indicating that changes of the “slow” state variable x are controlled by an adaptation function $g(V, x)$ with the characteristic time τ_k .

For the calculation of synaptic properties, we will use a CALM model formed by the equations²³

$$V = R_s I_{tot} + u, \tag{3}$$

$$I_{tot}(u) = [g_L + (g_H - g_L)x]u + C_m \frac{du}{dt}, \tag{4}$$

$$\tau_k(u) \frac{dx}{dt} = x_{eq}(u) - x. \tag{5}$$

Here, R_s is a series resistance and u is the voltage in the device. C_m is a constant capacitance that produces a fast-charging response. x_{eq} is a sigmoidal function so that $x \rightarrow x_{eq}$ in equilibrium (when $\dot{x} = 0$). The rapidity of equilibration of x to external stimuli is proportional to the reciprocal of the relaxation time τ_k . The device conduction current, which represents the synaptic weight, is tracked by the variable x , which changes the conductance between a low value g_L (at $x = 0$) and a high value g_H (at $x = 1$). The characteristic behavior of hysteresis in current and x -variable under voltage cycling is shown in Fig. 1.

The special property of the model (3)–(5) is the linear behavior of the differential equations in the x -variable, while the nonlinearity occurs in the functions $x_{eq}(u)$ and $\tau_k(u)$ that define a particular model according to the material properties.²³ This quasi-linearity feature is physically satisfied if the concentration of ionic species forming the activated conductance is proportional to the conductivity.¹¹ The model is validated experimentally in several types of memristors,^{12,28,32–35} and it is widely used in neuronal dynamics.^{36,37}

FIG. 1. Hysteresis in a quasi-linear memristor model. (a) IV curves and (b) memory variable x under sinusoidal stimulation $u = U_0 \sin(\Omega_s t)$ at amplitude $U_0 = 1.5$ V and cycling frequency $f_{\Omega} = 0.2$ Hz. Panel (a) indicates the low (cyan) and high (purple) conductance branches and panel (b) the model functions $x_{eq} = 1/(1 + e^{-(u-V_{Br})/V_m})$, $\tau_k^{-1} = \tau_M^{-1} + \tau_0^{-1} \left(\exp\left(\frac{u-V_A}{n_A V_m}\right) + \exp\left(-\frac{u-V_D}{n_D V_m}\right) \right)$. Model parameters: $g_L = 0.1$ mS, $g_H = 1$ mS, $V_m = 0.1$ V, $\tau_0 = 1$ ms, $\tau_M = 1$ ms, $V_{Br} = 0.5$ V, $V_A = 1$ V, $V_D = -1$ V, $n_A = n_D = 2$, $R_s = 20$ Ω , and $C_m = 0.05 \times 10^{-9}$ F.

The voltage train of identical pulses in Fig. 2(a) is normally used to test the synaptic plasticity.^{9,13,20,38} A pulse $V_0 \rightarrow V_1 \rightarrow V_0$ is applied for a duration Δt_p , followed by a rest time Δt_r , and then it is repeated. We are interested in the extent of synapse excitation or inhibition at the end of $(n + 1)$ pulses, at the time $t_{nf} = (n + 1)\Delta t_p + n\Delta t_r$.

The property (5) of the model means that $x(t)$ can be readily integrated, provided that $u \approx V$, which occurs if the initial capacitive spike is fast, i.e., $\Delta t_p, \Delta t_r \gg R_s C_m$,³² this restriction is discussed later. Then we have, for a transition from states $A \rightarrow B$,

$$x(t) = x_B + (x_A - x_B)e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_B}}. \tag{6}$$

Consequently, during the *on* time of the train in Fig. 2(a), the synapse weight changes from the initial value $x_0 = x_{eq}(V_0)$ toward the final value $x_1 = x_{eq}(V_1)$ controlled by the relaxation time $\tau_1 = \tau_k(V_1)$. During the *off* time, the variable tends to x_0 under a relaxation time $\tau_0 = \tau_k(V_0)$. Let us define

$$\alpha = e^{-\frac{\Delta t_p}{\tau_1}}, \tag{7}$$

$$\beta = e^{-\frac{\Delta t_r}{\tau_0}}. \tag{8}$$

The changes of x in Fig. 2(a), starting from $x(t_{0i}) = x_0$, are

$$x(t_{0f}) = x_1 + (x_0 - x_1)\alpha, \tag{9}$$

FIG. 2. (a) Voltage schedule for potentiation and variation of the x variable. (b) Current, (c) x and (d) a variation for the model of Fig. 1 with $\Delta t_p = 10$ ms, $\Delta t_r = 10$ ms, $V_{Bx} = 0.4$ V, $V_A = 2$ V, $\tau_0 = 1$ ms, $\tau_1 = 1$ ms. In panel (b), the orange line represents the conduction current, the blue line represents $u(t)/2$, and the magenta constant line represents the total current $I_{tot}(V_1)$. In panel (c), x represents the orange line, and the green lines represent x_0, x_1 .

$$x(t_{1f}) = x_1 + (x_0 - x_1)\alpha[1 - \beta(1 - \alpha)]. \quad (10)$$

These changes can be characterized by a function $a(t)$ defined by

$$a(t) = \frac{x_1 - x(t)}{x_1 - x_0}. \quad (11)$$

Here, $a = 1$ indicates no change of the state, while $a = 0$ marks the complete forgetting of the initial state. For the values $a_n = a(t_{nf})$ we can obtain

$$a_0 = \alpha, \quad (12)$$

$$a_1 = \alpha[1 - \beta(1 - \alpha)], \quad (13)$$

$$a_2 = \alpha(1 - \beta(1 - \alpha[1 - \beta(1 - \alpha)])), \quad (14)$$

and so on.

The linearity of the response represented by Eq. (6) can be confirmed experimentally by the purely exponential form of the rise and decay when the pulses do not interact, namely if $\Delta t_p \gg \tau_1, \Delta t_r \gg \tau_0$, see Figs. 2(b) and 2(c), such that x reaches the respective saturation value before the end of the interval. Therefore, $a(t) = \exp(-t/\tau_1)$ during the rise time, as shown in Fig. 2(d).³⁹ Note that the current in Fig. 2(b) is zero during the off part of the cycles, but the decay of the conductance value x (often measured by a small read voltage) is exponential as well, as shown in Fig. 2(c).

Now we understand in detail how the internal memory variable of the system evolves on a pulse-by-pulse basis. In other words, we can describe the temporal interactions between the excitatory post-synaptic currents (EPSCs) generated by the device and the incoming spikes.¹¹ This framework encompasses most of the key synaptic properties typically evaluated in memristive systems, such as potentiation (learning), its analog depression (forgetting), PPF, SRDP, and others.

III. PREDICTING CONVERGENCE VALUES

In conventional potentiation measurements, the focus is placed on the learning capability and the emergence of multilevel states (i.e., analog memory capacity) in the synaptic devices after the application of a train of voltage pulses with well-defined amplitude, temporal spacing, and duration. During these experiments, the system responds with a sequence of EPSCs, each progressively enhanced, until the conductance converges toward a stationary maximum value. This maximum equilibrium current (or conductance) is determined by the interplay between the temporal parameters of stimulation and the intrinsic potentiation capability of the system.^{40–43} Both the magnitude of this saturated state and the number of pulses required to reach it are critical descriptors for the evaluation and design of neuromorphic devices. They provide practical guidelines for selecting optimal operating voltages and communication timescales across different network architectures and application domains.⁴⁴

Following the analytical developments introduced earlier, these potentiation measurements can be anticipated from the model parameters already defined. By monitoring the temporal evolution of the system response a , we observe that the progression follows a recurrence relation described by the equation

$$a_n = \alpha(1 - \beta) + \alpha\beta a_{n-1}. \quad (15)$$

By substitution, we find the expression

$$a_n = \alpha(1 - \beta) \left[\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (\alpha\beta)^k \right] + (\alpha\beta)^n a_0. \quad (16)$$

Since $\alpha\beta < 1$, when n becomes large, we can apply the geometric series summation, and we obtain

FIG. 3. Synaptic potentiation in the model of Fig. 1. Representation of the current (orange, left) and x -variable (orange, right). $V_0 = 0.2$ V, $x_0 = 0.05$, $\tau_0 = 0.97$ ms, $V_1 = 1.2$ V, $x_1 = 1$, $\tau_1 = 0.98$ s. (a) $\Delta t_p = 0.1$ s, $\Delta t_r = 0.05$ s, (c) $\Delta t_p = 0.05$ s, $\Delta t_r = 0.2$ s. [(a), (c)] The magenta line is the full current $I_{tot}(V_1)$. The blue line is $u(t)/2$. [(b), (d)]. The green line is x_1 , the short red lines are $x(t_n)$, and the dashed red line is the potentiation convergence value x_F . (e) Period dependence of the convergent value of potentiation. (f) Frequency dependence of the gain.

$$a_F = \frac{\alpha(1-\beta)}{1-\alpha\beta} \quad (\text{for } n \gg). \quad (17)$$

Using Eq. (17) together with Eq. (11), we can extract the numerical value of the convergence of x after a given potentiation pulse train, $x(t_F) = x_F$. Specifically, the values of $x(t_n)$ using Eq. (17) are shown in Fig. 3(b) (short red lines), and they provide a very good approximation to the x -value after each voltage step. The dashed red line is x_F and describes very well the stabilized value of x in potentiation.

Connected directly with the potentiation, a widely used experimental procedure to probe synaptic devices is to apply short pulses followed by longer rest periods, as shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d).^{13,20,45} The dependence of the convergence value x_F on the period of the stimulus $T = \Delta t_p + \Delta t_r$ is shown in Fig. 3(e) by changing the inter-pulse time Δt_r at fixed Δt_p . The frequency dependence in SRDP⁴⁶ can be obtained from the period as $f = 1/T$. The gain after n pulses is given by

$$G = \frac{x(t_{1f})}{x_0} = \frac{x_1}{x_0} + \left(1 - \frac{x_1}{x_0}\right) a_n, \quad (18)$$

and the convergence value is

$$G_F = \frac{x_1}{x_0} + \left(1 - \frac{x_1}{x_0}\right) \frac{\alpha(1-\beta)}{1-\alpha\beta}. \quad (19)$$

The $G_F(f)$ at different values of Δt_p is shown in Fig. 3(f). This function is frequently measured experimentally, with results that are very similar to those in Fig. 3(f).^{9,47}

IV. EXPERIMENTAL TRENDS OF CONVERGENCE VALUES IN POTENTIATION

Previously, we have mentioned the experimental observation of this saturation, as illustrated in studies such as that shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b).⁴⁰ Beyond this qualitative evidence, if the fitting parameters of our model are obtained from a specific experimental system, we are now able to predict the convergence quantitatively.

As an example, we consider a nanofluidic memristor based on a nanoporous membrane integrated into an electrochemical cell. This system provides a highly reproducible response and has already been extensively characterized and fitted.²⁸ In Fig. 4(c), we can

FIG. 4. [(a) and (b)] Experimental evidence of the saturation effect that appears in potentiation processes across different types of memristive devices. Reproduced from N. Ilyas *et al.*, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **15**, 30 (2020), licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).⁴⁰ (c) Experimental potentiation of a nanofluidic memristor²⁸ obtained by applying voltage pulse trains with 2 ms duration and 2 ms interval at the voltage amplitudes indicated in the legend. Solid lines correspond to the EPSC response to the pulses, while dashed lines represent the theoretical convergence. The parameters used for the calculation of the theoretical convergences are given in the [supplementary material](#), Table S1.

clearly observe this convergence: apart from small deviations that may arise from device variability or degradation during cycling, the predicted potentiation matches very well the experimental measurements. This result demonstrates that the analytical model not only describes the temporal evolution of the synaptic weight but also captures the experimentally accessible stationary limit of potentiation with remarkable fidelity. For a more detailed understanding of the experimental procedure and the calculations performed to obtain Fig. 4(c) in full, the reader is referred to the [supplementary material](#). The initial spikes in Fig. 4(c) correspond to the fast capacitive response. They do not affect the longer evolution of the synapse, which is due to an chemical inductive mechanism.⁴⁸

V. PROPERTIES OF PAIR-PULSE FACILITATION

We now turn to one of the most fundamental and widely studied synaptic properties, PPF. In this protocol, two identical pulses are applied, with the same duration and amplitude, separated by a controlled time interval, that is systematically varied. The synaptic modification observed between the first and the second response is defined as PPF.

In the historical development of PPF measurements, two equivalent definitions have consistently been employed, both offering similar interpretations of the underlying effect. The first is the

increase ratio in current (or conductance) between the final currents of the first and the second pulse responses

$$PPF(\%) = \frac{I_1}{I_0} \times 100, \tag{20}$$

and the second is the *relative* increase,

$$PPF(\%) = \frac{I_1 - I_0}{I_0} \times 100. \tag{21}$$

As shown in the equations, both quantities are commonly expressed as percentages by multiplying their values by 100. These definitions have been widely adopted in both natural synaptic systems and artificial memristors,^{19,49–51} as they provide the most straightforward and experimentally accessible descriptions of the phenomenon.

It is important to emphasize, however, that the PPF value obtained is strongly dependent on the initial conductance state of the device. Even if the potentiation is significant, a device that starts from a high baseline conductance (high g_L or x_0) will exhibit a smaller PPF compared to another device with lower initial conductance (low g_L or x_0) but the same potentiation capability. Figure 5 provides a graphical clarification of this dependence, as well as guidance on how PPF data should be interpreted in practice.

FIG. 5. Simulation of [(a)–(c)] EPSCs obtained under the application of a pair of identical 2 V pulses separated by $\Delta t_r = 1$ ms, with varying pulse widths Δt_p , and (d) PPF for the same three pulse widths Δt_p of [(a)–(c)], evaluated as a function of the interpulse interval Δt_r . The dashed lines show the separation between the pulse maxima I_1 and I_0 , both highlighted in green.

One might assume that making pulses longer always increases potentiation and, therefore, PPF, but it does not. Each device has a specific pulse-width window that maximizes PPF; widths shorter or longer than this window reduce facilitation. This has two key implications for interpreting experiments: (i) you must first identify the time window in which the device actually potentiates and (ii) the measured PPF is strongly influenced by the device's baseline conductance. Consequently, PPF values should not be compared naively across devices and are best treated as qualitative indicators rather than strict quantitative benchmarks.

In order to assess the validity of the analytical calculations of the temporal evolution of x and their application within the model, we simulated this synaptic property for the previously discussed nanofluidic memristor. Two equivalent approaches, as shown in Fig. 6(a), were employed: direct application of Eqs. (7)–(10) into Eq. (21) for the evolution of the internal variable and explicit simulation of the memristor response to voltage pulses, using Eqs. (3)–(5), followed by the extraction of the maximum currents and calculation of PPF in the same way as in experiments, Eq. (21). As shown in Fig. 6(a), both methods lead to fully equivalent results, confirming that the analytical description of x is entirely valid.

We then compared these simulations with experimental measurements under identical excitation conditions, as illustrated in Fig. 6(b). A difference in absolute magnitude can be observed, which may arise from several sources: small discrepancies in the relaxation time obtained from impedance spectroscopy compared to that obtained under pulsed operation, or uncertainties in mapping theoretical states to experimental conductance extrema when extracting PPF values. Despite this quantitative deviation, the overall shape of the PPF curves, as well as their trends with respect to pulse width and interpulse spacing, are faithfully reproduced. This consistency demonstrates the predictive power of the

model and its robustness in describing experimental short-term plasticity.

At this stage, it is useful to think beyond the standard definition of PPF in Eqs. (20) and (21) and to address some of its intrinsic limitations. Since PPF is expressed as a percentage, it is inherently dependent on the initial state of the device. For instance, when a train of 1 V pulses is applied, each pulse, including the very first, starts from a baseline current that already reflects the intrinsic conductance of the device at that voltage. In our model, this corresponds to the current that the system would exhibit at 1 V if no potentiation had yet taken place starting from 0 V, as given in a voltage-dependent form by

$$I_b(u) = g_L x_0 u. \quad (22)$$

Introducing this baseline current as a reference parameter allows us to reformulate the definition of PPF in an analogous way,

$$PPF(\%) = \frac{I_1 - I_b}{I_0 - I_b} \cdot 100 = (1 + \alpha\beta) \cdot 100, \quad (23)$$

$$PPF(\%) = \frac{I_1 - I_0}{I_0 - I_b} \cdot 100 = \alpha\beta \cdot 100. \quad (24)$$

We can see how the defined PPF quantities are connected to the general framework described earlier. This is because, in this new definition, the outcome no longer depends on the initial conductance state or the absolute potentiation strength of the system. Instead, it is governed exclusively by the dynamic evolution of the internal memory variable and by the temporal characteristics of the applied pulses, namely their width and separation. In principle, this alternative formulation directly resolves the limitations of the classical PPF definition. In this way, the measurements can be compared

FIG. 6. (a) Simulation of the PPF obtained from the memristive system, calculated both by directly simulating the current response to voltage pulses (points) and from the analytical evolution of the internal variable x under a pulse sequence (lines). (b) Experimental PPF measured in a nanofluidic nanopore-based memristor. Reproduced from G. Rivera-Sierra *et al.*, J. Am. Chem. Soc. **147**, 17529–17538 (2025), licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).²⁸ In both cases, PPF values were obtained by applying a series of 1 V pulses with four different pulse widths, indicated in the legends.

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across a wide variety of synaptic systems, including natural neurons, since they also follow models analogous to those discussed above, such as the Hodgkin–Huxley formalism.^{37,52} This unified framework enables the identification of both dynamic ranges and optimal magnitude values, providing meaningful benchmarks across different neuromorphic applications.

VI. DISCUSSION

The analytical recurrence in Eqs. (15) and (16) captures a central practical point of pulse-driven learning: under repeated stimulation, the synaptic state evolves toward a *stationary limit* that is fully determined by two quantities: (i) the device’s intrinsic potentiation response to a pulse (bundled in α) and (ii) the degree of retention/relaxation during the interpulse interval (encoded by β). Solving the recurrence gives the closed-form convergence factor in Eq. (17), which, together with Eq. (11), yields the stabilized state x_F and the corresponding gain G_F in Eq. (19). In other words, once α and β are identified for a given voltage amplitude, pulse width Δt_p ,

and rest time Δt_r , the endpoint of potentiation and the number of pulses required to approach it are predictable rather than empirical.

The transient approach to the fixed point is equally informative. From Eqs. (15)–(17), the sequence satisfies

$$a_n = a_F + (\alpha\beta)^n (a_0 - a_F), \quad (25)$$

so the distance to the limit decays geometrically with ratio $\alpha\beta$. This gives a simple design rule for how many pulses are needed to reach a tolerance ε from the limit,

$$n \gtrsim \ln \frac{(\varepsilon/|a_0 - a_F|)}{\ln(\alpha\beta)}. \quad (26)$$

Therefore, both the ultimate level and the speed of convergence are tunable knobs linked directly to the device parameters and pulse timing.

Importantly, the initial capacitive spikes typical of two-terminal systems do not affect the slower dynamics that govern synaptic

FIG. 7. (a) Simulated PPF response of the memristor under study, obtained from pulse-driven excitation using Eqs. (22)–(24). (b) Theoretical PPF derived directly from the analytical expression $PPF = \alpha\beta$. (c) Experimental PPF of the same memristor, after subtracting the baseline conductance at the applied voltage as determined from the parametric fit of the 2 V curve, $I_b = 1.6 \mu\text{A}$. (d) Experimental PPF obtained after subtracting a slightly larger baseline conductance, approximately $I_b = 2.1 \mu\text{A}$, showing the strong sensitivity of this definition to the baseline value.

plasticity and can be regarded as a fast overlay. Only at very high frequencies, or when both pulse widths and separations are extremely short, does incomplete capacitive relaxation lead to an artificial conductance increase. In most devices, however, the timescales are well-separated, and this interference is negligible.^{42,53}

Practical implications follow directly. Since x_F and G_F depend on the pulse width Δt_p and the interpulse interval Δt_r , devices exhibit operating windows where gain is maximized while energy use and stress are minimized. Expressing the results in terms of α, β, x_F, G_F , provides a consistent benchmark across technologies, avoiding the variability inherent in raw conductance steps. The framework extends naturally to devices with multi-timescale dynamics, where recurrence relations generalize to sums of exponential modes while retaining closed-form predictability. In real devices, cycle-to-cycle drift or degradation may shift the parameters modestly, but these effects can be incorporated as confidence intervals.

Turning to PPF, the standard definitions of Eqs. (20) and (21) express facilitation as ratios of successive responses. While convenient, these values depend strongly on the device's initial conductance and, therefore, complicate comparisons across devices or even cycles of the same device. This issue is also present in biological neurons.^{17,18,24} The baseline-referenced formulation of Eqs. (22)–(24) overcomes this by subtracting the intrinsic baseline current so that PPF reflects only the device's potentiation capacity. Theoretically, this reduces to a product of exponentials determined by pulse timing and device dynamics, providing a universal metric. In practice, however, its application is limited by the precision required in determining the baseline conductance: even small uncertainties can dramatically shift the calculated PPF, as illustrated in

Figs. 7(c) and 7(d). Figure 7(c) shows the experimental PPF extracted using the baseline conductance obtained from the 2 V fitted curve, while Fig. 7(d) demonstrates how shifting this baseline produces a dramatically different PPF response, now consistent with the simulations.

In summary, the recurrence framework transforms device evaluation from empirical trial-and-error into predictive design. By fitting α and β , one can determine stationary potentiation, frequency-dependent gain, convergence speed, and PPF behavior. For clarity and reproducibility, PPF values should be reported alongside the device's initial conductance and, when possible, complemented with a baseline-referenced metric. This dual reporting preserves continuity with the literature while enabling fair, state-aware comparisons and more rational neuromorphic device design.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we established an analytical framework to describe the temporal evolution and stationary convergence of synaptic weights in quasi-linear memristive systems under pulsed stimulation. By deriving closed-form expressions for paired-pulse facilitation, convergent potentiation, and frequency-dependent gain, and validating these predictions with experimental data from a nanofluidic memristor, we demonstrated that the dynamic behavior of complex synaptic devices can be accurately captured using a simple, universal formalism.

Beyond its immediate application to memristors, this approach provides a unifying language for describing synaptic plasticity across diverse systems, including biological synapses that share analogous relaxation-based dynamics. It offers a powerful tool to disentangle

the intrinsic device properties from their operational conditions, enabling direct comparisons between heterogeneous technologies and bridging the gap between biological and artificial synapses. By clarifying the fundamental rules governing synaptic weight evolution, this framework can accelerate the rational design of neuromorphic circuits and guide the development of next-generation computing architectures that harness the full richness of synaptic plasticity.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The [supplementary material](#) encompasses a fluidic nanopore-based memristor fit and potentiation application.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Gonzalo Rivera-Sierra: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Juan Bisquert:** Conceptualization (lead); Investigation (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (lead).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data presented here can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17159696> (Zenodo) under the license CC-BY 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International).

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